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“WHEN MA’AM BECAME MOM”

In a blink, she carried you
Cold hands, trembling heart,
Questions louder than the dark.
Would she survive?
Would love stay?

Tears fell before courage came.
Judgment burned like flame.
Yet in the chaos, grace appeared—
She was accepted, not feared.

She prayed through swollen nights,
Through whispers and silent fights.
Then heaven answered in a way so sweet
An email from DepEd, complete.
A permanent post, a growing womb,
Fear and blessing sharing one room.

Labor came like a storm of knives,
Pain screaming through fragile life.
But when she heard your cry,
The world hushed into a lullaby.
Ma’am was no longer just a name—
She was Mom, forever changed.

For 105 days, she held you close,
Milk-stained shirts and gentle hopes.
No lesson plans, no classroom noise,
Just tiny fingers and softer joys.

Then the bell rang once again.
Goodbye, full-time Mommy.

Hello, Ma'am.

She taught with steady voice,
But her heart ran home each hour.
Postpartum shadows followed her,
Yet she stood in quiet power.

Students said, "We missed you, Ma'am."
But all she longed to hear was "Mom."
Between chalk dust and lullabies,
She learned how sacrifice survives.

At night she planned tomorrow's class,
Then held you like time would pass too fast.
She was not always okay
But love made her stay.

By day, she answered to "Ma'am."
By night, she answered to "Mom."
And in between the bell and the cradle,
She faced each challenge, steady and able.

